

AQLI ZAIF O'QUVCHILARNI ELEMENTAR MATEMATIK KO'NIKMALARNI KUNDALIK HAYOTDA QO'LLASHGA O'RGATISHDA PEDAGOGIK QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH

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ABSTRACT

Mazkur maqolada aqli zaif o'quvchilarda elementar matematik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish hamda ularni kundalik hayot jarayonlarida qo'llashga o'rgatishda pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlashning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Tadqiqot davomida maxsus ta'lim jarayonida qo'llaniladigan samarali metodlar, amaliy mashg'ulotlar, ko'rgazmali vositalar va individual yondashuvlarning o'quvchilar rivojiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, son-sanoq, vaqtni aniqlash, pul birliklari bilan ishlash, xarid qilish va oddiy hisob-kitoblarni bajarish kabi hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari bayon etilgan. Maqolada o'quvchilarning mustaqil hayotga moslashuvi, ijtimoiy faolligi va amaliy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash muhim omil ekanligi asoslab beriladi.

Pedagogical support plays an important role in organizing the educational process for students with intellectual disabilities. This is because students with intellectual developmental impairments possess specific characteristics in their cognitive activity, thinking processes, and level of social adaptation. Therefore, the process of teaching such students to acquire elementary mathematical skills and apply them in daily life requires a purposeful pedagogical approach and systematic support. Pedagogical support refers to a system of pedagogical influences aimed at helping students overcome difficulties arising during the learning process, developing their individual abilities, and ensuring their success in educational activities. This process is carried out through the teacher's cooperation with students, the selection of appropriate methods and techniques according to their developmental level, and the adaptation of the educational process. One of the main tasks of pedagogical support in teaching students with intellectual disabilities mathematical knowledge is to stimulate their cognitive activity. Such students often demonstrate unstable attention, slow perception processes, and delayed development of thinking operations. Through pedagogical support, it is important to increase students' interest in learning activities, encourage independent thinking, and guide them toward applying knowledge in practical activities. Teaching students to apply mathematical skills in everyday life primarily

requires an individualized organization of the educational process. Since each student differs in developmental level, learning pace, and psychological characteristics, the teacher must provide pedagogical influence while taking into account their individual abilities. In this process, it is important to identify students' strengths, develop them, and use methods aimed at eliminating existing difficulties. During pedagogical support, the teacher not only provides knowledge but also develops students' independent activity skills. In the process of teaching the application of elementary mathematical skills in daily life, developing students' independence and initiative is of great importance. These skills play a significant role in their future social adaptation and ability to live independently. Strengthening students' knowledge is also essential within pedagogical support. Students with intellectual disabilities often tend to forget learned material quickly. Therefore, it is necessary to reinforce knowledge through regular repetition, application in various situations, and connection with practical activities. This process helps to form stable mathematical skills in students. The teacher's observational activity also plays an important role. The teacher should regularly analyze the process of students' knowledge acquisition, identify at which stage they encounter difficulties, and provide the necessary pedagogical assistance. Such an approach helps to identify problems in students' educational activities in a timely manner and eliminate them effectively. Establishing cooperation with parents is also an important component of pedagogical support in teaching students with intellectual disabilities to apply mathematical skills in everyday life. Parents' active participation in their children's education and involving them in performing simple calculations in daily life help strengthen students' mathematical skills. Therefore, it is advisable for teachers to maintain regular communication with parents and provide them with methodological recommendations. As a result, students develop skills such as performing simple mathematical operations, comparing quantities, and working with time and money units. This serves as an important factor in their social adaptation and preparation for independent living.

1. Methodology for distinguishing volumetric features
2. Methodology for working with logical problems
3. Methodology for developing number and quantity skills
4. Methodology for developing geometric perception
5. Methodology for understanding space and time

An individual approach is used in teaching students with intellectual disabilities. In the process of forming elementary mathematical concepts and skills for applying them, students learn in everyday life mainly through the direct perception of material models of geometric shapes and objects from surrounding reality. It is observed that students with intellectual disabilities often have underdeveloped components of activity, including need-motivational, meaningful, operational, and productive aspects. Therefore, these characteristics should be taken into consideration when organizing the system of lessons and the lessons themselves:

- interesting and engaging lessons;
- frequent changes in types of classroom activities;
- influence on all analysis systems (visual, auditory, and kinesthetic);
- presentation of educational material in small portions;
- slow pace for studying topics;
- frequent repetition of the studied material.

Lessons are organized on an integrated basis using various types of activities: games (role-playing, didactic, movement-based, dramatized games), labor activities (manual and household work), constructive activities, and visual activities (drawing, clay modeling, and appliqué). Conditions are created during lessons that allow each student to work independently and at a comfortable pace. The material is selected and organized according to the complexity level and the individual developmental characteristics of each student. Through practical actions and repeated performance, students prove their assumptions and strengthen the knowledge and skills they have acquired. Students observe the work of the teacher or one of their classmates using visual aids. In mathematics lessons, every child should independently work with individual handout materials. When using the observation method in presenting new knowledge, it is necessary to determine beforehand what students should observe and which features they should pay attention to. Observation should be organized in such a way that students arrive at specific conclusions. Students themselves should participate in drawing conclusions. Observation skills in students with intellectual disabilities are significantly reduced. To achieve the desired results, it is important to guide observations, organize questions systematically, and direct attention toward the essential features that distinguish one object or number from another.

Practical activity with objects (working with hands) enables students to study the characteristics of an object more deeply and comprehensively, better understand its important qualities, and remember them more effectively. Therefore, when studying material, the observation method should be combined with the teacher's explanation and the practical activities of students. In the formation of elementary mathematical concepts and skills for applying them in daily life among students with intellectual disabilities, didactic games should occupy an important place as a teaching method.

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